

Training role in Financial mechanisms to enhance entrepreneurship Evidence from CNAC mechanisms in Tlemcen region.

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Abstract:

The aim of our paper is to clarify the role of the CNAC (Caisse National d'Assurance chomage) in training, informing and preparing the unemployed people about entrepreneurship, finance the project of the individuals who want to launch activity, and by the different facilities followed, the number of the entrepreneurs' growth to achieve highest numbers.

As a result of the previous empirical study in Tlemcen in the period 2005-2012, we find that the facilities play an important role in the sector of activity and the gender of the entrepreneur. We found that there is an important in the transport enterprises for the male entrepreneurs more than female entrepreneurs, where in the services sector and handicraft, the number of female entrepreneurs is nearly as the male entrepreneurs.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, training, facilities, CNAC, Tlemcen, finance.

Jel Classification Codes : G21, G28.

المخلص:

نسعى من خلال هذه الورقة البحثية إلى توضيح دور الصندوق الوطني للتأمين على البطالة CNAC في تعليم، تدريب وإعداد البطالين حول معنى ومتطلبات المقاولاتية، تمويل مشروعات الأفراد الذين يريدون خوض غمار إنشاء المقاولات وإبراز مختلف التسهيلات الموضوعية من أجل تمويل وتسهيل عملية خلق مؤسسة، حيث وجدنا أن إعداد المقاولين وصلت إلى مستويات تنبؤ بوعي المقاولين حول أهمية المقاولات في خلق الثروة والنمو بالاقتصاد المحلي.

وكنتيجة للدراسة الميدانية السابقة التي أجريتها في تلمسان، توصلنا إلى أن التسهيلات التي وضعتها الدولة أدت دوراً جوهرياً في خلق المقاولات بالنسبة إلى كل من الجنسين، الأمر الذي يبين دور المرأة وأحقيتها في خلق مؤسساتها المصغرة، بالإضافة إلى نوع العمل من خلال إعطاء الحرية للفرد باختيار نوع العمل حسب مهاراته.

الكلمات المفتاحية:

المقاولاتية، التدريب، التسهيلات، CNAC الصندوق الوطني للتأمين على البطالة، تلمسان، تمويل

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1. Introduction:

According to (Allen, Otchere, & Senbet, 2011), the financial system plays an important role in the state because it is the heart of financing the different activities in two sides:

The macro side: it is the side related to the government and the state activities such as big construction and industries and so on.

The micro side: this side is related to the small and medium size enterprises created by the individuals following the different mechanisms in each country.

To pursue the economic growth in the world, entrepreneurship is one of the important key factors for the growth of the different economies. According to (Stefanescu & On, 2012), they find that sustainable entrepreneurship is related to the sustainable development. In addition to push the entrepreneurship following different studies to know the different obstacles and the different barriers faced by the individuals to create their own small enterprises. According to (BOUROUHA Abdelhamid, Maliki Samir Baha Ed-dine, & Derbal Abdelkader, 2014), they mention that the individual find different obstacles are related especially to the sources of finance.

The paper is organized as follows. In section two, we will demonstrate the importance of the financial mechanism in enhancing entrepreneurship; in the third section, we will demonstrate some of the different financial mechanisms in Algeria that are ANSEJ, ANGEM and CNAC. In the fourth section, we will make a global view of the growth of the number of entrepreneurs through CNAC dispositive in Tlemcen.

finally, conclusion to summarize the benefit of the financial mechanisms CNAC in financing enterprises.

2. Methods :

Algerian Financial mechanisms for entrepreneurship:

As we mention above, and according to the importance of entrepreneurship in the economic growth. In addition to the different studies that are turn around the difficulties that it faces the individual to create own enterprise, the Algerian government start to invest in this sector by taking the mission of financing the new enterprises created by the individual through creating different mechanisms. From these mechanisms, we will give a quick overview of three mechanisms:

ANSEJ¹:**Following different official gazette from 1993 to 2011:**

- Presidential Decree No. 96-234 of 2 July 1996, on support for youth employment, supplemented by Presidential Decree No. 11-100 of March 6, 2011.
- Executive Decree No. 96-295 of 8 September 1996 fixing the operating procedures of the Trust Account No. 302-087 entitled "national fund to support youth employment," modified and completed by Executive Decree 03 -74 of 23 February 2003 and Executive Decree No. 04-231du August 4, 2004.
- Executive Decree No. 96-296 of 8 September 1996 establishing and determining the constitution of the national agency to support youth employment, modified and supplemented by Executive Decree No. 01-162 and Executive Order No. 03-288 of 06 September 2003 and Executive Decree No. 11-102 of March 6, 2011.
- Executive Decree No. 98-200 of 9 June 1998 establishing and determining the statute of mutual guarantee fund risk / credit young promoters, modified guaranteed and completed by Executive Decree No. 03-289 of 6 September 2003.
- Executive Decree No. 03-290 of 06 September 2003 setting out the conditions and the level of support given to young promoters, as amended by Executive Decree No. 11-103 of March 6, 2011.
- Executive Decree No. 10-157 of 7 Rajab 1431 corresponding to 20 June 2010 amending and supplementing the Executive Decree No., 03-290 of 9 Rajab 1424 corresponding to 6 September 2003 setting the conditions and level of assistance to young entrepreneurs.

3. Results and Discussion :**Type of loans in ANSEJ dispositive:**

The ANSEJ was created as a financial mechanism to finance the project of the new entrepreneurs through two different types of finance with a condition that the sum of loan will not be superior to 10 million da:

The triangular type of finance: the sum of the loan will be divided between three: the bank, the ANSEJ PNR without interest and the personal part.

The mixed type of finance: in this type of finance, the role of the bank does not exist

The table below present a clear picture about the rates for each type of finance:

¹ANSEJ : Agence Nationale de Soutien à l'Emploi des Jeunes

Table 1: different types of loan

	The sum of loan	The triangular type of finance	The mixed type of finance
Personal part	Less than 5 million DA	1%	71%
	5 million and 10 million da	2%	72%
ANSEJ part	Less than 5 million DA	29%	29%
	5 million and 10 million da	28%	28%
Bank part	Less than 5 million DA	70%	None
	5 million and 10 million da	70%	None

Source : <http://www.ansej.org.dz/>

The figure below presents the growth of the number of entrepreneurs through the two different types of loan:

Figure 1: growth of financed project by type of finance

Source : <http://www.ansej.org.dz/?q=fr/content/nos-statistiques>

Following the figure 1, we understand that the most important barriers that is face the individuals to create their own enterprises is money a source of finance, there for we find that there is a big difference between the number of triangular types of loans and mix type of loans. According to this important, the table 2 shows the growth of the number of enterprises through ANSEJ from 2007 till 2013:

Table 2: The growth of financed project through ANSEJ mechanism

Year	To 31-12-2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	Total
Financed project	86380	10634	20848	22641	42832	65812	43039	292186

Source : <http://www.ansej.org.dz/?q=fr/content/nos-statistiques>

1.1. Sector of activity and ANSEJ dispositive:

From the most important steps that the ANSEJ make them is to allow the individual to choose the appropriate sector, the table 3 show us the segmentation of the enterprises through sector of activity:

Table 3:the growth of financed project by sector

Sector	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	total
agricultureand fishing	10668	814	1467	2222	3686	6705	8225	33787
Handicraft	13380	1881	3455	3264	3559	5438	4900	35877
Construction	4013	933	2078	2794	3672	4375	4347	22212
industry and manufacturing	6333	1247	1685	1542	2118	3301	3333	19559
Services	51986	5759	12163	12819	29797	45993	22234	180751
total	86380	10634	20848	22641	42832	65812	43039	292186

Source : <http://www.ansej.org.dz/?q=fr/content/nos-statistiques>

As in the figure bellow, we find that the big rate of enterprises focused in the sector of services according to the easiest sector of work, in the second place we find handicraft especially in the agricultural regions.

Figure 2: the growth of financed project by sector

Source : <http://www.ansej.org.dz/?q=fr/content/nos-statistiques>

Gender and entrepreneurship at ANSEJ dispositive:

Concerning the categories interested with the dispositive, ANSEJ does not make obstacles for gender (between male and female). This latest is a positive step because that it creates variety in the sectors of activities because there are some activities such as hairdresser and dressmakers for both genders men and women.

Table 4: growth of project financed by gender

gender	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	Total
female	12166	1502	2496	2211	2951	4477	3526	29329
Male	74214	9132	18352	20430	39881	61335	39513	262857
Total	86380	10634	20848	22641	42832	65812	43039	292186

Source : <http://www.ansej.org.dz/?q=fr/content/nos-statistiques>

As it appears in the figure bellow, there is a huge difference between the number of male entrepreneurs and the female entrepreneurs the point that it confirms that the male takes risks more than female, in addition the ability of the male in taking decision and managing enterprises. This latest result is confirmed with the study of (Haus, Steinmetz, Isidor, & Kabst, 2013) where they found that the male have an entrepreneurial intention more than women.

Figure 3: growth of project financed by gender

Source : <http://www.ansej.org.dz/?q=fr/content/nos-statistiques>

ANGEM²:

In the second point, we find that there is another mechanism that finances the individuals to create their own enterprises. Following the different facilities for enhancing the individual to create their own enterprises, the Algerian government makes different policies through these decrees:

- Presidential Decree No. 04-13 of 22 January 2004 on the system of micro-credit.
- Executive Decree No. 04-14 of 22 January 2004 establishing and determining the status of the national agency management of microcredit, as amended and supplemented by Presidential Decree No. 08-10 of 27 January 2008.
- Executive Decree No. 04-15 of 22 January 2004 laying down the conditions and the level of assistance provided to recipients of micro-credit, as amended and supplemented by Executive Decree No. 11-134 of 22 March 2011.
- Executive Decree No. 04-16 of 22 January 2004 establishing and determining the status of the mutual guarantee fund micro-loans.
- Executive Decree No. 05-414 of 25 October 2005 laying down the operating procedures of the CAS No. 302-117, as amended and supplemented by Executive Decree No. 09-84 of 17 February 2005.

The different thing in this mechanism is that it does not need that the individual is unemployed, in addition to the not limit of age.

²Agence Nationale pour la Gestion du Micro-crédit

Types of finance in ANGEM mechanism:

There are three types of finance in ANGEM mechanism as it shown in the table below:

Table 5: different types of finance

Type of finance	Sum of loan	Personal part	PNR part	Bank part	Interest rate
Mixed type	Less than 30 000.00 da	10%	90%	0%	0%
	Between 50 000.00 and 100 000.00da	3% or 5%	0%	95% to 97%	Interest reduced with 80% to 90%
Triangular type	Between 100 001.00 and 400 000.00da	3% or 5%	25% to 27%	70%	Interest reduced with 80% to 90%

Source : <http://www.wilayadjelfa.dz/>

From the table 5, there are two types of finance:

Mixed type: this type also divided into two types through the sum of loan

1- *The mixed type of finance with some less than 30000.00da:*

The ANGEM mechanism make this loan for the individual who do not need much loan for activity according to the small activity, in addition to the inexistence of the interest rate.

2- *The mixed type of finance with some between 50 000.00da and 100 000.00da:*

We find that in this type, the sum of loan is divided between the personal part characterized in a rate between 3% and 5% following some condition like sector of activity and region. About the interest rate, there is a reduction in the interest rate between 80% and 90% according to the sector of activity.

Triangular type:

The triangular type of finance is between three dispositive: ANGEM, personal part and bank. The bank part is 70% with interest rate reduced with 80% to 90% according to the sector of activity and the region. The personal part and the PNR part also related with the place and the sector of activity, for that we find that there are two value of the rate for every part.

As in the other dispositive, the ANGEM mechanisms allows both genders male and female. The table 5 shows the segmentation of the enterprises through gender until 31june 2014.

Table 6: Number of beneficiaries by gender

Gender	Number	Rate
Female	384063	61,70%
Male	238418	38,30%
Total	622481	100%

Source :<http://www.angem.dz/>

To complete the explication, the figure bellow shows us the rates of segmentation per the gender (male and female).

Figure 4: circle for rates of entrepreneurs through gender

Source :www.angem.dz

After the segmentation per gender where we find that ANGEM allows both gender male and female in getting loans and launching activities.

Sector of activity through ANGEM dispositive:

To know the different activities launched through loan from ANGEM, the figure 6 presents the different sectors of activities launched by the ANGEM mechanism/ we find that there is a diversification in activities. From this point, we understand that the role of this mechanism is to help the majority of the individual to get loan and launch their activities. In the first, we find the small activities with 234401 activities from the creation of the mechanisms until 31/06/2014. Second, the services activities with a sum of 129960 activity. Last, we find that fishing also gets a sum of loan characterized in 374 loans.

Figure 5: segmentation of loans through sector of activity

Source: <http://www.angem.dz/>

The CNAC mechanism:

The idea of creating CNAC dispositive in the first is to help the involuntary unemployed people in the period after the shock in the hydrocarbon prices; it was created through the presidential decree 188-94 in July 06, 1994. After that, and by the appearance of the important role of entrepreneurship as a key for sustainable development in the developed countries. According to (Kardos, 2012), the sustainable innovation and sustainable development is interrelated with the growth of sustainable entrepreneurship. There for, In December 30, 2003, the Algerian government added a new option in the CNAC mechanisms that is financing the project of the unemployed people because the lack of financial resources is the big problem in the face of the individual to launch his or her enterprises.

The CNAC facilities:

To facilitate the way for the unemployed to become entrepreneur, the Algerian government follows different facilities to enhance the unemployed for entrepreneurship. From these facilities, we find different kinds that are related with the different steps of the creation of the enterprise.

A. Before the creation:

The CNAC mechanism takes different to facilitate the procedure for the individuals before the creation of the enterprises by a formation.

- **The training:**

Despite the growing body of literature in the field of entrepreneurship, there is still considerable uncertainty as to whether entrepreneurs are born or made, which has led to an ongoing debate in the entrepreneurship academy about whether we can actually teach individuals to be entrepreneurs (Henry, Hill, & Leitch, 2005). Also, following the importance that it faces the entrepreneurship education

over the world, in addition to (von Graevenitz, Harhoff, & Weber, 2010) where he found that student has entrepreneurship education are more likely to be entrepreneurs rather than the ones who has not this courses. Also, according to (Sondari, 2014) who find that the entrepreneurship education get an important role in creating entrepreneurial intention in the student. From another side and according to (Dhar, 2015) "the training can be defined as a planned and systematic effort to modify or develop knowledge, skill, and attitude through learning experience, to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities". Through this definition, it is considered that the training has an important effect on the creation of enterprises. In addition and following the study of (Hynes, 1996), the training and entrepreneurship-education are from the important factors to launch the entrepreneurship especially in the fields that have not knowledge about business because they will be the idea's generators for business. Following this importance, the Algerian government invest in this field by the creation of financial diapositives with the offered training and formation to create the entrepreneurial ideas in the mind of the unemployed and to clarify the entrepreneurial procedure in the future.

B. In the creation process:

After the step of the formation where the individuals have got the important information about the world that they will enter, the step of the folder creation. In this step, the Algerian government make other facilities in the way of reducing the barriers in the face of the unemployed of becoming entrepreneur. This reduction characterized in:

C. The CSVF³ committee:

Before, in the first step of the procedure of the creation, the individuals find different obstacles in the way of satisfying the bankers for the credibility of the project, where in some situation, the entrepreneur was obliged to use his personal relation to get the loan of the bank. There for, the government creates the CSVF committee that it contains delegates from the banks, the CNAC mechanism, and the civic state delegates in addition to the entrepreneur. For that, this committee from the important facilities that it helps the individuals to get loan to launch his project.

³CSVF : comité de Suivre, Validation et de Financement.

- **Reduction in the personal part:**

From the big obstacles that it faced the unemployed to get loan and become entrepreneur through CNAC mechanisms is the personal part. Because, in the first the procedure of financing the project was as in the table below:

Table 7: Segmentation of sum of loan in the first

	Personal part	CNAC part	Banc Part
Less than 5.000.000,00 AD	5%	25%	70%
Between 5.000.000,00DA and 10.000.000,00DA	10%	20%	70%

Source: www.cnac.dz

After that, and according to the different demands of the individuals how have entrepreneurial skills but they do not have much money for the personal part. It reduced the personal part to a minimum sum as it is presented in the table to allow the maximum number of unemployed to get loan and create their own enterprises:

Table 8: new segmentation of the sum of loan

	Personal part	CNAC part	Banc Part
Less than 5.000.000,00 AD	1%	29%	70%
Between 5.000.000,00 AD and 10.000.000,00 AD	2%	28%	70%

Source :<http://www.mf.gov.dz/article/300/Grands-Dossiers/255/DISPOSITIF-CNAC.html>

- **Reduction in the interest rate:**

To satisfy the needs of the individuals wanting to become entrepreneur, the Algerian government offer some special reduction in the interest rate in addition to the reduction that it touches all individuals who get loan from CNAC dispositive. This reduction related with two points:

- ✓ **Sector of activity:**

The CNAC mechanism offers reduction in the rate of interest in normal sector with 50%. The rate of reduction could be equal to 75% if the sector of activity one of these sectors:

Agriculture, irrigation and fishing sector. This policy used to enhance the individuals how has such skills and experience in these domains to invest in these sectors.

- ✓ **Place of activity:**

Through the diversified regions in the Algerian countries where the big surface is so difficult to stay in, the Algerian government give these

places some special important in the goal of investing in these regions. There for, the rate of decreases is as follows:

In the special areas, the rate of decrease in the interest rate is 90%

In the South and high plateau, the rate of the decrease is 75%.

D. After the creation of the enterprise:

To complete the procedure of felicitating the way for the new entrepreneurs in the market, the Algerian government think also in the market that they will inter, therefor it creates a special part for this category of the entrepreneurs:

- **Create a part of them in the market:**

According to the different obstacles, that it faced the enterprises especially in the sector of manufacturing and construction. Following the presidential decree 12-23 in January 18, 2012, The Algerian government makes rate of 20% of the offered project for the new entrepreneurs as a step to help them in the market in front of the high level of competition.

- **Taxes reduction:**

After the creation of the enterprise and through the previous obstacles faced by the new enterprises that are related with the taxes, the Algerian government exempt the new entrepreneurs in the first three years from the taxes below:

IRG⁴: Exemption from the tax on gross income

IBS⁵: Exemption from tax on the profits of the company

TAP⁶: Exemption from the tax on professional activity

TFPB⁷: Exemption from real estate tax based on property

Exploratory view of CNAC entrepreneurs in Tlemcen 2005-2012:

The CNAC mechanism contribute with an important rate in creating entrepreneurship in Tlemcen. The figure bellow shows the growth of the number of entrepreneurs in the period 2005-2012

⁴IRG : Impôts sur revenue global

⁵IBS : Impôts sur les bénéfiques des sociétés

⁶TAP : Taxe sur l'activité professionnelle

⁷TFPB : taxe foncière sur les propriétés bâties

Figure 6: growth of entrepreneurs through CNAC in Tlemcen 2005-2012

Source: www.cnac.dz

In the first, we found that the number of entrepreneurs was 41 entrepreneurs. From this point, we understand that the individual is interested to be self-employee. According to the important rate of the female in our society, we found also that she enters to the entrepreneurial world inside the man. The table below presents the segmentation of the number of the entrepreneurs per gender:

Table 9: segmentation of CNAC entrepreneurs by gender

Gender	Number	Rate %
Male	2137	89.12 %
Female	261	10.88 %
Total	2398	100 %

Source: www.cnac.dz

From this table, we understand that the female gets the ability as the man to get loan and to create her enterprises, to show to the world that she is also apt to take risks as the man. Also, she has got also her personal skills in some special sector, for that she finds the financial mechanisms to finance her projects.

Growth of entrepreneurs per sector of activity:

From the different facilities, that the Algerian government makes to encourage the individual to become entrepreneur is to allow him to choose the sector of activity according to his desirous. As we show in the table below, the entrepreneurship through CNAC mechanism, touches different sectors. From the ones that it does not need just driving license, in the case for the enterprises of transport to the sectors of industry and

construction where it is necessary the existence of the experiences, skills and special diploma to launch an enterprise in these kinds of activities.

Table 10: growth of entrepreneurs per sector of activity in tlemcen 2005-2012

year	industry	agriculture	Services	transport	Handicrafts	Construction	total
2005	2	5	7	16	4	7	41
2006	5	13	7	47	5	9	86
2007	5	8	4	74	6	14	111
2008	2	13	7	98	5	9	134
2009	2	6	6	162	4	16	196
2010	0	7	5	228	2	11	253
2011	1	5	8	488	7	14	523
2012	13	49	25	925	5	37	1054
total	30	106	69	2038	38	117	2398

Source: www.cnac.dz

From the table above, we find that the number of the new entrepreneurs in the last year (2012) is the most important with more than 1000 new entrepreneurs. As a result, we understand that the different of the CSVF committee and the reduction in the personal part push the individuals to create their own enterprises. For the different sectors of activity, we find that the majority of the enterprises are focuses in the transport sector with more than 85%. For more detail, the figure below clarifies the segmentation of the entrepreneurs by sector of activity:

Figure 7: segmentation of enterprises per sector of activity

Source: www.cnac.dz

As we said before, the highest rate of the entrepreneurs focused in the transport sector according to the facility in the folder of getting loan. In the second rate, we find that the enterprises in construction and manufacturing in the second place with 117 entrepreneurs, this is related to the facility of 20% of project for the new entrepreneurs. The agriculture placed in the third place with 106 according to the difficulties of the sector of activity.

Table 11: segmentation of sector of activity per gender

	Industries	Agriculture	Services	Transport	Handicraft	Manufacturing
Male	22	81	37	1859	24	114
Female	8	25	32	179	14	3

Source: www.cnac.dz

The table above shows the segmentation of entrepreneurs through sector of activity and gender. We find that the female entrepreneurs founded in all sectors as the male entrepreneurs, the matter that it confirms the ability of taking risks in front of the man, but with different rates according to the skills of the gender. For example, the rate of the female entrepreneurs is nearly like the male entrepreneurs' rate (32 entrepreneur

and 37 entrepreneurs respectively). In addition, the female entrepreneurs contribute also in the domain of handicraft by exploiting their personal skills as hairdresser and dressmaker.

Conclusion:

From this paper, we find that the Algerian policy takes a big step in investing in the private entrepreneurship through different mechanisms such as ANSEJ, ANGEM and CNAC. Through CNAC, we find that its role in the first is to help the unemployed involuntary through the changes in the economic and the industrial structure in the nineteen decades. After discovering the importance of the entrepreneurship in the economic growth following (Li, Yang, Yao, Zhang, & Zhang, 2012) and entrepreneurship and economic development following (Toma, Grigore, & Marinescu, 2014). From the different barriers faced the individuals to create their own enterprises is the sources of finance. Therefore, the Algerian government invest in the private entrepreneurship by offering training for the unemployed person to have the necessary knowledge about business. In second step, the government create more facilities to finance the project of the unemployed people. Through the data gathered, we find that these financial dispositive plays the role of the key for the entrepreneurship engine.

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